

IPBES BBA Chapter 4 – Approaches for measurement of business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and ecosystems – Uptake analysis / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (Section 4.5)

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Description

This data processing task was conducted to inform section 4.5 in Chapter 4 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment. The aim was to assess the extent to which businesses apply methods for assessing dependencies and impacts, as analysed in Chapter 4.

The Alphasense document search platform¹ was used to perform searches across a database of company publications. The sources included major SEC, FDIC, FERC, global filings, environmental, social, and governance reports, investor presentations, earnings presentations, and other business reports published in the year 2024. More details on the data sources selected in Alphasense are provided in the additional files, one for impact and one for dependencies analysis.

Authors responsible for impact measurement defined a set of keywords representing metrics for measuring business impacts and a separate set of keywords for methodologies and stressors. Authors responsible for dependency measurement defined sets of keywords representing dependency terminology and method descriptions, as well as names of individual ecosystem services, and tools.

To investigate the evolution of uptake over time, authors also performed a longitudinal analysis. Same data sources were used as for the analysis of 2024 records. We quantified the evolution of records from the beginning of Alphasense records (beginning of 2005) to the present day (end of 2024).

After the search, the dataset extracted from Alphasense was supplemented with missing information on GICS sectors and IPBES regions.

Results in the form of numbers of reports published per keyword, numbers of companies publishing reports per keyword and number of reports published per keyword were used to compile tables and graphs for section 4.5, and an addendum.

¹ <https://www.alpha-sense.com/platform/>

Overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Keyword search in business reports, indexed in the Alphasense database.
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Alphasense
- **Search Dates:**
 - 6 June 2025 for Impacts
 - 7 August 2025 for Dependencies
- **Search terms:**

For measurement of impacts:

Topics: Biodiversity impact; Biodiversity loss; Nature related risk; Nature's Contribution to People

Guidance: TNFD OR SBTN OR LEAP Approach

Methods: carbon footprint OR greenhouse gas footprint; water footprint; LCA OR Life Cycle Assessment; biodiversity footprint; biodiversity impact assessment; Integrated Assessment Model; MRIO OR EMRIO; General Equilibrium Model; Participatory mapping; Corporate biodiversity footprint; Field survey AND biodiversity; Spatial overlay; biodiversity and life

Pressures: Land use OR Land use change; greenhouse gas emissions OR GHG emissions; invasive species; land occupation OR land transformation; overexploitation; biodiversity AND land use change; drivers of nature change; sea use change; Biodiversity AND sea use change

Tools: ENCORE AND impacts; Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool OR IBAT; ENCORE AND dependencies; biodiversity risk filter; global biodiversity score; (LC-Impact OR IMPACT+ OR ReCiPe) AND Biodiversity; High impact commodity list; SBTN materiality screening tool; Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade Offs OR INVEST

Several keywords did not result in hits, and are therefore not included in the results.

For measurement of dependencies:

Topics: natural capital; Biodiversity; ecosystem services; nature-related risk; Natural Capital AND Ecosystem Services; Dependencies on nature; Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities risks and exposure; Benefits of nature; nature's contribution to people

Guidance: TNFD OR SBTN OR LEAP Approach

Methods: Natural Capital Accounting; LCA AND dependencies; Ecosystem AND (economic valuation OR monetary valuation); (EMRIO OR (Input/Output model)) AND dependencies; Ecosystem AND non-monetary valuation; Integrated Assessment Model AND ecosystem services

Services: water supply; freshwater; water purification; pollination; genetic diversity; erosion control; recreation* services; biomass AND provision*; Biological pest control OR Biological disease control; soil quality AND regulating; recreation AND ecosystem service

Tools : Aqueduct; water risk filter; biodiversity risk filter AND dependencies; Ecosystem Services Valuation Database; Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs OR INVEST

For the longitudinal analysis:

Only a few keyword trends were selected for section 4.4, namely footprint methods that show uptake of different footprint subjects (GHG, water, biodiversity).

Depending on the keyword, the impact analysis yielded 13126 keyword hits in reports published by 2 to 500 companies. The dependency analysis yielded 8439 keyword hits in reports published by 1 and 520 companies. The longitudinal analysis going up to the year 2024 yielded up to over 54.000 results in company documents, on carbon footprints while biodiversity footprints were found 500 times.

The raw keyword hits (A) were first cleaned, and IPBES country names and GICS sector names were assigned based on different types of information (i.e. domain names, or cities of headquarter). This cleansing and data standardisation was necessary as the raw data of the Alphasense results is incomplete or given at different levels of aggregation (GICS sectors or industries / region or domicile country). Processed results were summarised to tables (B) with the help of pivot tables, corrected for duplicates and not relevant results (Pivot fields: region and sector / Results: count of unique companies).

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_4.5_08-2025_(A)	.csv	2.962KB	Background raw data extracted from the Alphasense data for both impacts and dependencies.
B	IPBES_BBA_4.5_08-2025_(B)	.csv	31 KB	Final results after processing of raw data
C	IPBES_BBA_4.5_08-2025_(C)	.csv	37 KB	Trends in number of documents that mention different footprint methods.